

FINAL REPORT

Alaska Microgrid Innovation and Commercialization & Workforce Development

Alaska Center for Power and Energy
University of Alaska Fairbanks

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Alaska Center for Energy and Power

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Abstract

The overarching goals for this project were (1) to increase remote microgrid-relevant expertise at the Alaska Center for Energy and Power (ACEP), (2) to improve interaction with remote system utilities and increase relevance of research, (3) to provide a venue where industry partners may be supported by ACEP in improving their microgrid-relevant products, and (4) to ensure workforce readiness for a transition from traditional diesel-based power generation systems to advanced microgrids with heavy reliance on power-electronics, automation, and optimal control.

To achieve those goals, we focused on two primary vehicles. The *Alaska Center for Microgrid Technologies Commercialization (ACMTC)* was seed funded by a U.S. EDAi6 award to ACEP. The center was leveraged with the help of this award as a competition mechanism to determine technology needs, identify and surmount hurdles to commercialization and develop enabling technologies of benefit to utilities and solution developers. We conducted two rounds of the ACMTC competition (in 2017 and 2018) and awarded 125 hours of consultation to three companies and 65 hours of technology and integration testing in the Power Systems Integration (PSI) laboratory.

The second vehicle is a training program, the *Arctic Remote Energy Networks Academy (ARENA)*. We initiated the ARENA program in 2017 to increase communication between stakeholders in the arctic to understand requirements, interfaces and challenges associated with both existing microgrid systems and those that are evolving in the eight member-states and twelve observer-nations within the Arctic Council. Eighteen current and emerging energy professionals participated in the pilot program.

The award was modified in 2019 to shift focus of the remaining funding to a workforce development objective. We initiated the *ACEP Utility Internship* program to provide a combined research and workforce development platform for collaborations between the ACEP, Arizona State University (ASU), Alaskan utilities, rural campuses in the state, research initiatives and industry partners. The internship program was conducted over the following three years and was expended in each year to better meet our goals and objectives. The program is currently being re-designed to meet the requirements for an NSF REU site.

Accomplished Task Summary

TASK 1: OUTREACH

The goal of this task was to identify stakeholders and engage with researchers, local communities and technology experts to develop and accelerate affordable, reliable and renewable energy solutions in remote communities of the Arctic, and potentially other remote areas of the world. We focused on two objectives for this task: research and development of technologies suited to small microgrids in remote areas of the Arctic via the ACMTC competition; and community energy expert skill development and support via the ARENA program. The respective task leaders build up a sizable pool of interested parties and stakeholders to design, initiate and execute the two programs and make them successful. This work included extensive outreach to various stakeholders, from community leaders to energy, power electronics and social researchers, and to industry experts, to broaden our understanding of the regulatory, financial and social challenges for the rural communities as well as the technical challenges of the integration of renewable energy sources at the microgrid level.

For more information on the results of this task, see the below task descriptions.

TASK 2: ARENA

We responded to a need for the development of community energy experts to ensure affordable, reliable, and renewable energy solutions for Arctic communities by initiating the *Arctic Remote Energy Networks Academy (ARENA)* program. The goal of ARENA is to build capacity, share knowledge and initiate network building for the establishment of sustainable energy solutions in remote communities in the arctic and, potentially, other remote areas of the world.

For the ARENA pilot program in 2017, eighteen individuals from communities and organizations across the Arctic (Alaska, Canada, Greenland, and Russia) were selected by the Arctic Council's Sustainable Development Working Group. Among them are nine Alaskans, coming from communities as far separated as Sand Point and Fort Yukon, Kodiak, and Kotzebue. The program was put on hold due to COVID-19 restrictions on travel and is commencing with a new cohort in 2022. The new cohort contains eighteen participants from four countries (Alaska, Canada, Greenland, and Russia). More information about ARENA is available at arena.alaska.edu.

ARENA 2017

In collaboration with researchers and subject matter experts from across the Arctic, ARENA provided training related to sustainable energy development in Arctic communities. We developed a broadly accessible webinar series that introduces viewers to the remote energy networks (microgrids) that provide power and heat across the Arctic. The series is comprised of six modules:

- Remote Energy Networks in the Arctic
- Diesel Power Plants
- Variable Renewable Energy Resources in the Arctic –Solar
- Variable Renewable Energy Resources in the Arctic – Wind

- Integrated Energy Perspectives – Heat Generation and Distribution (Part I & Part II)

The series can be accessed here: <https://arena.alaska.edu/2017webinars/>.

A select group of eighteen individuals participated in the pilot project that combined laboratory demonstrations with visits to communities and sites operating with renewable energy resources in Canada, Alaska, and Iceland between March and November 2017. Each geographic location focused on key individual elements of clean energy generation.

Figure 1: 2017 ARENA participants at UAF/ACEP location in Fairbanks, Alaska

The program consisted of three on-site programs and an outreach session at the Arctic Energy Summit. The first on-site program was hosted by Canada and conducted in Yellowknife, Northwest Territories, from March 20-27, 2017. The second on-site program was hosted by the United States in Fairbanks and Kotzebue, Alaska, from June 17 to 24, 2017. The program then conducted an outreach event at the Arctic Energy Summit in Helsinki, Finland, on September 18-20, 2017, during a ‘Capacity Building’ session. Three ARENA participants presented on their projects during the session. The final part was the on-site program hosted by Iceland in Reykjavik, from November 5 to 11, 2017.

The onsite programs consisted of course work covering energy project development and implementation objectives and provided site visits to energy projects in rural communities. The course work provided participants with background knowledge on various energy planning related topics such as resource assessment, measuring and monitoring resources, financial management, governmental regulations and successful stakeholder engagement with city and tribal councils, governmental agencies, utilities and rural communities. The Yellowknife course focused on wind and solar projects with a strong community development perspective. Microgrid systems and

integration of distributed energy sources was the primary objective of the Alaska on-site session. ARENA participants attended the 2017 Alaska Wind-Diesel Conference in Fairbanks during their stay. The agenda for the on-site session in Iceland focused on providing the participants an understanding of the development and utilization of geothermal energy.

Figure 2: Power Systems Integration (PSI) laboratory demonstration session for ARENA participants

ARENA set up a mentoring program where each ARENA participant was aligned with another professional whose experience and organizational context complemented and/or supplemented the resources already available to the participant. The mentors were aligned with participant priorities as stated in their applications.

More information is available on the Arctic Council Working Group ARENA website:
<https://sdwg.org/what-we-do/projects/arctic-remote-energy-networks-academy-arena/>

The “Arctic Remote Energy Network Academy (ARENA) Achievements Report” for ARENA 2017 can be accessed here:

https://oaarchive.arctic-council.org/bitstream/handle/11374/2300/SAOFI204_2019_RUKA_07-01-08_SDWG_Report-ARENA.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y

Outcomes/Future Work

The 2017 ARENA program was highly successful and achieved its goal of connecting energy champions from remote Arctic communities, increasing skill and knowledge about remote energy systems and enabling collaboration networks between participants, mentors and rural communities. The second ARENA program was slated for 2020 but had to be postponed due to COVID-19 travel restrictions. The program is now continued this year (ARENA 2022) under other external funding.

The participants have been selected and the site visitation planning is currently ongoing. More information on ARENA 2022 can be found here: <https://arena.alaska.edu/2020/>.

TASK 3: RESEARCH

To accelerate the transition of microgrid-relevant technologies from innovation to implementation, we provided a platform for interactions of utility partners and technology developers in conjunction with renewable energy integration technology expertise at the Alaska Center for Energy and Power. This platform, called the *Alaska Center for Microgrid Technologies Commercialization (ACMTC)* was established by ACEP, the Alaska Small Business Development Center, and the Center for Economic Development. The effort was seed funded by U.S. EDA and funds provided by the State of Alaska. This additional award allowed us to coordinate a competition for emerging microgrid technologies. The objective was to work with various Alaskan, national and international partners with the goal of identifying required key developments needed to increase renewable energy contributions, reducing the cost of energy and providing stable and secure energy in a resilient grid.

ACMTC Competition

ACEP, through ACMTC processes, established the ACMTC Competition, an open call for proposals to utilize the Power Systems Integration (PSI) team and lab for R&D, design reviews, support with component specification and selection, and development of plans for product hardening for austere environments, as well as a limited amount of in-system testing in the PSI Lab. The competition included Technology Seed (up to 5 awards, for up to 125 hours of consultation), and Microgrid Project (up to 2 awards, up to 25 days of integration testing in the PSI Lab) awards to help companies move their technologies towards market availability.

As a first step, we announced our intent and collected ‘expressions of interest’. We received responses from 25 companies. The first round of the competition was advertised in July of 2016. We conducted two webinars during the summer where we presented the rules, discussed the application requirements and answered questions from webinar participants. The competition closed at the end of August 2016. We received a total of seven applications: five Technology Seed applications and two Microgrid Project applications. The applications were reviewed by an independent advisory team and three finalists were selected based on their recommendations: DONuT, Inc. and Energy and Ocean Renewable Power Company (ORPC) for the Technology Seed award and UniEnergy Technologies (UET) for the Microgrid award.

The following proposals were accepted:

DONuT, Inc.: Designing Optimized Networks of Microgrid Technologies

The company consisted of three Stanford PhD students, and they had partnered with HOMER Energy to “develop a design interface specifically suited for remote villages in Alaska so that community leaders in these villages can determine the benefits of renewable energy systems quickly and easily without needing to navigate the ensemble of assumptions in HOMER.” They used energy data sets from Nome, Cordova, Unalakleet, Eagle, and Kokhanok for this project and received expertise from

ACEP staff on a weekly basis during the project execution. The CEO, Dan Sambor, has recently completed his PhD at Stanford University on a project in Alaska in collaboration with ACEP.

Figure 1: Alaskan Village Annual Load Profiles (ACEP)
Red=Nome Blue=Cordova Grey=Elsewhere

Figure 3: Load Characterization from DONuT project report

ORPC: Advance Power Electronics for Remote Microgrids with Common Components to Support Multi-modal Energy Generation and Storage

The goal of the project was to optimize a grid integration strategy that most efficiently utilizes the power from the RivGen 2.0 Power System in Igiugig, Alaska to directly offset diesel fuel use. One of ACEP’s research engineers, Jeremy Vandermeer, completed the “Igiugig Electrical Energy Storage Sizing Study” in collaboration with ORPC. The project was successful, and we are working with ORPC on developing new technologies to this day.

UET: Demonstration of a Vanadium Flow Battery in Demanding Microgrid Environments

The goal of this project was to demonstrate the energy storage’s ability to reduce microgrid operating costs and improve grid stability. UET designed a series of tests intended to be representative of how remote, austere, or demanding microgrid systems operate in Alaska and beyond.

UET eventually declined the award. The company shifted gears toward the manufacture of the UET ReFlex™ DC module and the new product was not ready for testing before the end of our award.

The second round of the competition was conducted a year later, in the summer of 2017. We received eight ‘expressions of interest’ and a total of four final applications: three Technology Seed and one Microgrid Project applications. The independent advisory team recommended funding one Technology Seed award (Oklo, Inc) and one Microgrid award (Intergrid, LLC).

The following proposals were accepted:

Oklo, Inc.: Integrating Alaska-scale Nuclear Power in Rural Microgrids

Oklo proposed conducting a time series energy balance with an accounting for heating loads of their cost-effective, reliable, carbon-free micro nuclear reactors. ACEP completed a community energy analysis for Kotzebue, a microreactor CHP (combined heat and power) load estimation and a power plant analysis as part of this project. Oklo became one of Launch Alaska’s cohort after completion of

this project and has filed a combined license application to build and operate an Aurora fast neutron reactor at the Idaho National Laboratory site with the Nuclear Regulatory Commission (NRC).

Intergrid, LLC: Energy Storage Integration with Diesel Generation

Intergrid has designed a 70-kW inverter and proposed a testing and integration project with a ESS controller, a Woodward easYgen controller and an Ecoult 70 kWh battery bank. The project was revised when the physical inverter testing had to be delayed due to a global shortage of silicon carbide (SiC). The PSI program had obtained an Opal-RT based hardware-in-the-loop (HIL) platform at that point and the project scope was revised to HIL testing. Specifically, the team developed and validated three-phase inverter control algorithms using controller hardware-in-the-loop (CHIL), validated the integrated microgrid control approach using the same CHIL platform including actual easYgen genset controllers, and programmed support for the Programmable Logic Controller (PLC) based microgrid controller which included various dispatch strategies. The project was successfully concluded, and the inverter was later tested at the NREL facility in Boulder, CO. The inverter development was successful and is now going into mass production.

(<https://www.energy.gov/eere/wind/articles/competitiveness-improvement-project-awardee-fills-critical-gap-distributed-wind>)

Figure 4: ACEP's Opal-RT CHIL platform and the project team

Summary/Outlook

The competition drew a lot of interest in the beginning but did not attract a large number of high-quality proposals. The proposals we selected were successfully completed, except for UET who had to withdraw after a change in project design and development. Only a select number of company representatives from the original list of 25 interested parties applied for ACMTC awards. But the competition generated interest in our testing capability and facilities and we have been collaborating with several companies on research projects outside the competition (e.g. BladeRunner Energy).

PSI Laboratory Build-out

Part of the original EDA proposal was to build out the PSI laboratory on the University of Alaska Fairbanks campus. The lab enables technology developers to test their designs and provide additional resources for energy integration research. A 3-phase fault emulator was installed for this purpose and attracted attention for the ACMTC competition. (The device and the installation were not funded through this award but the original EDAi6 grant.)

Figure 5: Fault Emulator Testing in the PSI lab (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WwmTTtkKyLY>)

TASK 4: WORKFORCE DEVELOPMENT

The award was re-scoped in 2019 and the remaining funding was re-directed towards the ACEP Utility Student Internship program. The program was initiated in 2019 and evolved over the next three years from a barebones on-site program into a virtual program with multiple components. The virtual nature was related to COVID-19 restrictions and the program will be back to in-person internships as of this summer.

The program consists of three parts: the Alaska Energy Utility Lecture Series offered during the spring semester, a Microgrid Boot Camp offered in early May and summer internships for undergraduate students during the summer semester. The lecture series is a collaboration with the UAF Bristol Bay Campus, was first offered in 2020 and had a total of 22 participants that year. That number increased to 27 in 2021. The Microgrid Boot Camp is a collaboration with ASU/LEAPS and increased from 14 participants in 2019 to 19 in 2021. The internship accommodated nine undergraduate students in 2019, 10 in 2020, and 13 in 2021.

Goals

- Support of programs to develop the multi-skilled workforce required to design, install, operate and maintain the remote microgrids of the future.
- Provide a professional internship experience to participating students, including technical learning experiences outside the classroom and soft skills/professional development objectives.
- Connect ACEP research goals to utility/industry needs via internships and microgrid boot camp learning objectives.

Accomplished Work

- Alaska Energy Utility Lecture Series:

The lecture series is a 1-credit hour course through the UAF Bristol Bay Campus in Dillingham, Alaska. The lecture series introduces participants to operations, management, and employment in Alaska’s rural and urban utilities. Topics include: basics of electrical utilities, utility operations and training, challenges in renewable energy integration into small microgrids, Alaska Energy Authority Rural Utility Assistance program, and an introduction to microreactors in Alaska. Several presenters from rural utilities introduce their utilities, grid operations and integration challenges/successes. The class also provides a networking platform for students, government agencies, tribal entities, and utility companies.

- ACEP/ASU Microgrid Boot Camp:

ACEP, in collaboration with ASU and the UAF Bristol Bay Campus, conducted one in-person and two virtual boot camps over the last three years. The boot camps were 5-day intensive training programs consisting of a mix of lectures and virtual/real world hands-on exercises. The lectures covered electrical and thermal load estimation presentations and exercises, introduction to microgrids and mini-grids and a ‘design your own village microgrid’ exercise using the grid modeling software XENDEE. The in-person version used the PSI lab for hands-on exercises and the virtual version made use of newly available online resources and by us developed teaching materials for hands-on exercises: the use of a Power-The-Grid simulation game, a virtual powerhouse training exercise and a renewable resource assessment exercise.

Figure 6: ACEP/ASU Microgrid Boot Camp 2019 on the University of Alaska Fairbanks campus

- ACEP Utility Student Internships:

ACEP communicated with the utilities on specific needs in regard to workforce development and the result was an addition of several components to the internship program. We developed a new course layout which is documented in our *ACEP Internship Manual*. The manual covers all administrative information and extensive documentation on the two main training objectives: project management and professional development. The project management section uses guidelines by the Project Management Institute (PMI). We have developed templates for each process group for the students to use to plan, design and execute their summer project. The professional development training includes the creation of job application documents using an ePortfolio web application, presentations, and exercises on dealing with stress and conflict, professional communication, code of ethics, licensing of intellectual property and other select topics. We also practiced communication and networking during social hours with Alaska Center for Innovation, Commercialization, and Entrepreneurship (Alaska Center ICE) interns. Furthermore, we required the students to gain basic Python programming skills and obtained an educational license through DataCamp.com for that purpose.

The internships were mostly virtual for the past two years due to COVID-19 restrictions. Some interns traveled to remote locations for a short period of time and one internship was completely in-person with the electric utility in Sitka, AK.

The students wrote up a weekly progress report and meeting minutes. They gave practice presentations and received feedback on those from ACEP mentors and the other interns in the program. They submitted a final project report, several project management documents, completed three basic Python coding modules, and produced a vodcast detailing their internship for publication on the ACEP website.

We worked with a variety of partner utilities and organizations for our summer internships over the years, e.g. Cordova Electric Association (CEA), Alaska Power & Telephone (AP&T), Sustainable Energy for Galena Alaska (SEGA), City of Sitka Electric Department, Tanana Chiefs Conference and the City of Hughes, AK, Eaton Corp., Delta Wind Farm & Golden Valley Electric Association, Information Insights, Inc. & Solarize Fairbanks, Kawerak, Inc (Nome, Pilgrim Hot Springs, AK), Community Appropriate Sustainable Energy Security (CASES) Partnership, and the Communities of Shungnak & Ambler, AK.

All student projects and presentations from the last three years can be accessed here:
<https://ausialaska.com/>

The internships have provided an opportunity for ACEP to engage with utilities and research partners and provide valuable input, ideas and consideration for future research projects. They have also enabled various partners to connect with each other and device solutions applicable to the broader Alaska market, e.g., ETIPP and the City of Sitka.

From a workforce development standpoint, the internships provide an opportunity for the utility companies to train future engineers and have access to the student pool at the university.

Outcomes/Future Work

The resources provided through this grant enabled us to develop the internship program to engage undergraduate students with the research process and extend our capabilities to teach professional development and project management components. We applied for an NSF REU site award in the fall of 2021 and received notification that the proposal has been suggested for funding as of February 22, 2022. We are planning on extending the program to develop additional modules on energy security and resilience, cybersecurity, etc. with ASU LEAPS and integrating Teaching Through Technology (T3) components into the program next year. The T3 collaboration will enable us to develop a career pipeline for the T3 high school students as they interact with the undergraduate students from the internship program. We are also working on a project management boot camp component for the ARENA program for 2022.